

STATUS, CHALLENGES AND CONCEPTUALIZATION OF THE FUTURE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MINISTRY OF TRANSPORT – STATE TRANSPORT INSPECTORATE IN THE SEGMENT OF SAFE TRANSPORT OF PASSENGERS AND GOODS IN ROAD TRAFFIC

Stevcho Jolakoski

Faculty of Security – Skopje
stevco.jolakoski@uklo.edu.mk

Bojan Antić

Ministry of Transport – State Transport Inspectorate
bojan_antice87@yahoo.com

Lazo Matovski

Ministry of Transport – State Transport Inspectorate
lazomato@gmail.com

Abstract

This paper presents a theoretical and research-based overview and a synthesis of perspectives aimed at portraying the current state and conceptualizing the future development of an important institutional actor—the State Transport Inspectorate—in ensuring enhanced safety in the transport of passengers and goods in road traffic. Through data analysis and content analysis methods, the paper examines the existing operational and technical challenges faced by the Inspectorate. Furthermore, it proposes a conceptual framework for a future operational model within the Ministry of Transport in the domestic context, while positioning the Inspectorate as a modern European inspection service in a broader comparative perspective.

Keywords: *road traffic; passengers; goods; safety; State Transport Inspectorate.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The safety and security of passenger and goods transport in road traffic represent one of the most important components of the transport system. Their proper functioning and development have a significant impact on public safety, economic activity, environmental protection, and the overall efficiency of road traffic. Achieving a higher level of road traffic safety is a pressing issue and a strategic objective; however, empirical data and field observations often point to persistent shortcomings. The path toward improved safety is neither linear nor free of obstacles, but rather dynamic and complex, shaped by a multitude of institutional, legislative, personnel, and technical prerequisites, as well as—most importantly—by human behavior, awareness, and responsibility.

Synchronized inter-institutional cooperation and continuous inspection activities constitute essential prerequisites for prevention, the reduction of accidents and violations,

and the achievement of a higher overall level of road traffic safety. The network of actors responsible for ensuring road traffic safety and security is broad and interconnected. In addition to the State Transport Inspectorate, operating as a body within the Ministry of Transport, this network includes the Ministry of Transport itself—primarily through the Sector for Road Transport and Infrastructure—the Ministry of Internal Affairs, through the Department for Border Affairs and Migration and the Bureau for Public Safety (Traffic Sector), the National Border Management Center, the Customs Administration, the Public Enterprise for State Roads, and the Public Enterprise for the Maintenance of Main and Regional Roads.

Further contributors include educational institutions responsible for the training of technical personnel and the conduct of professional examinations, technical inspection stations and workshops performing analyses and checks across various segments of the road transport sector, national transport and carriers' associations, as well as driver training centers. Each of these entities, to varying degrees, contributes to ensuring safety, smooth traffic flow, and compliance with national legislation and internationally ratified legal instruments.

Within this framework, the State Transport Inspectorate occupies a particularly significant position. Through its supervisory, preventive, and repressive functions, the Inspectorate plays a crucial role in raising awareness among stakeholders, educating sector participants, identifying and addressing irregularities, and preventing future violations. These activities directly contribute to reducing the number of infringements, enhancing safety in the transport of passengers and goods, and improving overall road transport conditions at both national and international levels.

The impact of passenger and goods transport in road traffic is multidimensional, affecting safety, road infrastructure integrity, environmental sustainability, and economic flows. Minimizing or eliminating negative effects requires sustained investment in human resources and technical-operational capacities. This includes the recruitment of highly qualified professional staff, the deployment of advanced information systems and technological equipment for the detection and identification of violations, and the implementation of appropriate safety measures within the road traffic system.

2. THE STATE TRANSPORT INSPECTORATE THROUGH THE LENS OF MODERN DIGITAL REALITY

2.1. Legal Framework and Territorial Dispersion

Pursuant to Article 87-b of the Law on Road Transport²⁶, the State Transport Inspectorate is established as a body within the Ministry of Transport. Recent legislative interventions—namely the adoption and entry into force of the Law on Amending and Supplementing the Law on Inspection Supervision (*Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia* No. 272/24²⁷), the Law on Amending and Supplementing the Law on Inspection Supervision (*Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia* No. 22/25²⁸)

²⁶ “Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia” No. 68/04, 127/06, 114/09, 83/10, 140/10, 17/11, 53/11, 6/12, 23/13, 120/13, 163/13, 187/13, 42/14, 112/14, 166/14, 44/15, 97/15, 124/15, 129/15, 193/15, 37/16, 71/16, 64/18, 140/18 and 163/18 and “Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia” No. 275/19, 67/22, 170/24, 3/25, 17/25 and 101/25.

²⁷ The Law entered into force on 27 December 2024.

²⁸ The Law entered into force on 3 February 2025.

and the Law on Amending the Law on Road Transport (*Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia* No. 3/25²⁹) – have brought significant institutional changes.

As a result of these amendments, the State Transport Inspectorate remains an integral part of the Ministry of Transport but has lost its previous status as a legal entity with an independent budget account as a first-line budget user. Furthermore, the new Law on Inspection Supervision (*Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia* No. 135/25³⁰) which entered into force on 12 July 2025 and will apply from 1 January 2026, stipulates that state inspectorates may not be granted legal entity status by separate legislation. Instead, they independently manage the budget approved by the Ministry to which they belong, upon authorization by the Minister, and conduct employment procedures for inspectors in accordance with applicable law.

The headquarters of the State Transport Inspectorate is located in Skopje, with regional offices distributed across the municipalities of Tetovo, Gostivar, Kičevo, Gevgelija, Ohrid, Kočani, Sveti Nikole, Struga, Bitola, Kriva Palanka, Radoviš, Prilep, Kavadarci, Veles, and Berovo.

2.2. Organizational and Staffing Structure

The State Transport Inspectorate is headed by a Director appointed and dismissed by the Government. Internally, as a body within the Ministry of Transport, it is structured into two (2) sectors, each comprising two (2) departments, as illustrated in the organizational chart below.

Figure 1. Organizational Units of the State Transport Inspectorate

²⁹ The Law entered into force on 3 January 2025.

³⁰ The Law entered into force on 12 July 2025, but shall be applicable from 1 January 2026.

Source: Ministry of Transport, Analysis of the Organizational and Personnel Structure, Condition of the Vehicle Fleet and Inspection Supervision in the State Transport Inspectorate, p. 1.

Available at: <https://mtc.gov.mk/mk-MK/ministerstvo/drzaven-inspektorat-za-transport> (Accessed on 12 March 2025).

As of 1 March 2025, out of a total of 64 systematized job positions within the Inspectorate, 39 positions are filled, representing a staffing level of 60.94%. Of the 49 inspector positions, only 28 are filled (57.14%), while 11 of the 15 administrative (non-inspector) positions are filled (73.33%).

Figure 2. Quantitative Overview of Systematized and Filled Positions in the State Transport Inspectorate

Source: Ministry of Transport, Analysis of the Organizational and Personnel Structure, Condition of the Vehicle Fleet and Inspection Supervision in the State Transport Inspectorate, p. 2.

Available at: <https://mtc.gov.mk/mk-MK/ministerstvo/drzaven-inspektorat-za-transport> (Accessed on 12 March 2025).

Excluding the Director—who is appointed by the Government and is not classified as an administrative civil servant—the Inspectorate is clearly understaffed relative to the scope of its mandate. The inspector corps consists of only 28 inspectors, approximately half of whom are over 51 years of age, responsible for supervising road transport activities throughout the entire territory of the country. The 11 administrative employees display heterogeneous educational backgrounds and age profiles.

The Department for Road Traffic Inspection Supervision employs twenty (20) inspectors, including one (1) Head of Department (senior inspector), twelve (12) senior advisor-inspectors, one (1) independent inspector, two (2) assistant inspectors, and four (4)

junior inspectors. These inspectors are tasked with enforcing road transport legislation. The majority of violations are detected during field inspections conducted while transport operations are ongoing, although inspections are also carried out at company headquarters, other business premises, customs terminals, and border crossings. Both domestic and foreign legal and natural persons are subject to inspection supervision.

The Department for Public Roads, Cable Cars, and Ski Lifts Inspection Supervision includes eight (8) inspectors: seven (7) senior advisor-inspectors responsible for enforcing the Law on Public Roads, and one (1) senior inspector responsible for the application of the Law on Cable Cars and Ski Lifts. Their activities primarily involve field inspections of public roads, technical inspection stations, cable car installations, and ski lifts.

Table 1. Quantitative Overview of Inspector Staff in the State Transport Inspectorate by Type, Age, and Title (as of 1 March 2025)

Age → Level – Position ↓	Road Traffic					Public Roads					Cable Cars and Ski Lifts					Inspectors (Total)							
	<30 y.	31-40 y.	41-50 y.	51-60 y.	>60 y.	Total	<30 y.	31-40 y.	41-50 y.	51-60 y.	>60 y.	Total	<30 y.	31-40 y.	41-50 y.	51-60 y.	>60 y.	Total	<30 y.	31-40 y.	41-50 y.	51-60 y.	>60 y.
B1 – General Inspector						0						0						0	0	0	0	0	0
B2 – Chief Inspector						0						0						0	0	0	0	0	0
B3 – Assistant Chief Inspector						0						0						0	0	0	0	0	0
B4 – Senior Inspector		1				1						0						0	0	1	0	0	0
V1 – Advisor Inspector	0	0	4	4	4	12	0	1	2	2	2	7	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	6	7	6
V2 – Independent Inspector			1			1						0						0	0	0	1	0	0
V3 – Assistant Inspector			1	1		2						0						0	0	0	1	1	0
V4 – Junior Inspector	1	2	1			4						0						0	1	2	1	0	0
Total	1	3	7	5	4	20	0	1	2	2	2	7	0	0	0	0	1	1	4	9	8	6	

Source: Ministry of Transport, **Analysis of the Organizational and Personnel Structure, Condition of the Vehicle Fleet and Inspection Supervision in the State Transport Inspectorate**, pp. 2–3.

Available at: <https://mtc.gov.mk/mk-MK/ministerstvo/drzaven-inspektorat-za-transport>

(Accessed on 12 March 2025).

2.3. Segmented Responsibilities

The competencies and authorizations of the various profiles of state inspectors within the State Transport Inspectorate derive from the provisions of the Law on Road Transport, the Law on the Transport of Dangerous Goods in Road and Rail Traffic, the Law on the Working Time of Mobile Workers in Road Transport and Recording Devices in Road Transport, the Law on Public Roads, the Law on Cable Cars and Ski Lifts, and the Law on the Prohibition and Prevention of Performing Unregistered Activities, as well as from multilateral agreements and international treaties ratified by the Republic of North Macedonia.

In the segment of passenger and goods transport in domestic and international road traffic, state road traffic inspectors conduct supervision over a broad range of areas, including³¹:

- fulfillment of the conditions for obtaining licenses for inter-municipal and international passenger and goods transport;
- compliance with specific technical and operational requirements for vehicles used in different types of transport;
- implementation of agreements on joint inter-municipal line passenger transport concluded between one or more municipalities;
- passenger transport in inter-municipal road traffic;
- goods transport in domestic road traffic;
- supervision of legal entities, sole proprietors, and individuals engaged in international transport with regard to their obligations for verification and retention of copies of international transport permits;
- passenger and goods transport in international road traffic;
- special line passenger transport conducted between two or more municipalities or exclusively within a single municipality;
- inter-municipal taxi passenger transport; and
- bus stations and bus stops.

In contrast, state road inspectors (as distinct from road traffic inspectors) exercise responsibilities prescribed under the Law on Public Roads, which include the authority:

- to inspect and supervise the maintenance and protection of public roads and road facilities;
- to halt works carried out contrary to the provisions of the Law on Public Roads relating to the protection of public roads and road facilities and to order the *отстранување* (removal) of identified deficiencies;
- to order the remediation of deficiencies on public roads that endanger traffic safety or the stability of the road and road facilities;
- to suspend works carried out on or near public roads that may compromise road integrity or traffic safety;
- to exclude from traffic vehicles transported without a permit for extraordinary transport;

³¹ The specific competencies of state road traffic inspectors prescribed in the Law on the Transport of Dangerous Goods in Road and Rail Traffic and in the Law on Working Hours of Mobile Workers in Road Traffic and Recording Devices in Road Traffic are not the subject of this paper, but are of exceptional importance for the topic that is the subject of scientific observation.

- to order the demolition of facilities or parts thereof constructed within the road area or protective belt;
- to take measures to secure public roads and, where necessary, to temporarily prohibit traffic for certain categories of vehicles which, due to their technical characteristics, may damage the public road or, due to road conditions, may endanger traffic safety;
- to prohibit traffic on newly constructed or reconstructed public roads, their sections, or facilities thereon if they are placed into use without the required operating permit;
- to control whether temporary traffic regimes comply with approved traffic projects;
- to prohibit the use of parking areas or access roads on public roads if constructed without a permit or in contradiction to the issued permit;
- to supervise and control toll collection;
- to supervise and control the collection of fees for the use of public roads by motor and trailer vehicles, as well as fees for technical assistance on roads;
- to undertake other measures and actions within their competence under the Law on Public Roads; and
- to conduct inspection supervision in accordance with the provisions of the Law on the Prohibition and Prevention of Performing Unregistered Activities.

For the purposes of this paper, it should also be noted that the sole inspector for cable cars and ski lifts employed by the State Transport Inspectorate is responsible for supervising the condition of cable cars and ski lifts; overseeing the implementation of the provisions of the Law on Cable Cars and Ski Lifts relating to operational conditions; monitoring compliance with technical regulations, norms, and standards during construction and maintenance; and supervising works carried out on these facilities or within their protective zones.

2.4. Brief Summary of Passenger and Goods Transport and Inspection Supervision

Passenger and freight transport, by years

Figure 3. Passenger and Freight Transport (2010–2023³²)

Source: State Statistical Office

Web link:

https://makstat.stat.gov.mk/PXWeb/pxweb/en/MakStat/MakStat_Transport_PatenTransport/560_Trans_MK_T39_ml.px/chart/chartViewLine/?rxid=46ee0f64-2992-4b45-a2d9-cb4e5f7ec5ef. Accessed on 12 March 2025.

³² Since 2014, due to methodological changes, data on road passenger transport refer only to national and international transport. Since 2018, transit and cabotage have been included.

Figure 4. Three-Year Summary³³ of Inspection Supervisions and Detected Irregularities by the State Transport Inspectorate (2022–2024)

Source: *Ministry of Transport, Analysis of Organizational and Personnel Structure, Condition of the Vehicle Fleet and Inspection Supervisions in the State Transport Inspectorate*, p.3.

Web link: <https://mtc.gov.mk/mk-MK/ministerstvo/drzaven-inspektorat-za-transport>. Accessed on 12 March 2025.

3. CHALLENGES AND RISKS

The European Commission’s 2024 Report³⁴ on the Progress of the Republic of North Macedonia, published on 30 October 2024, contains a brief observation noting that the operational and technical capacities of the State Transport Inspectorate remain weak.

The identified challenges include an unfavorable quantitative and age structure of the inspector cadre; an extremely limited availability of highly trained non-inspector (administrative) staff to provide back-office or support services; a low volume of specialized theoretical and practical training; the loss of an independent budget account, particularly affecting the realization of capital investments; spatial and technical limitations in both the headquarters and regional offices; the absence of ISO standards and international certification for quality and process management; outdated stationary and mobile technical equipment; the lack of a central monitoring and data center with real-time analytics and data recovery systems; the non-implementation of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) along

³³ The graphic chart displays data from all areas of inspection competence of the State Transport Inspectorate.

³⁴ https://enlargement.ec.europa.eu/north-macedonia-report-2024_en. Accessed on 30 March 2025.

international road corridors; the absence of fully equipped road checkpoints for inspection purposes; insufficient safe parking spaces for heavy vehicles and buses during traffic stops; and an aging vehicle fleet. All of these factors impair traffic safety, monitoring, and the overall functionality of road traffic, and they undoubtedly have a negative impact on the scope and quality of the Inspectorate’s operational activities in the exercise of its powers.

For the purposes of this paper, particular attention is given to the issue of inspector mobility during field inspections through an analysis of indicators related to the quantity, age, and condition of the Inspectorate’s available vehicle fleet. This aspect will be further elaborated in Chapter 5, which addresses the implementation of a project aimed at modernizing the Inspectorate’s vehicle fleet with the support of grant funds from the European Union’s Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance 2021–2027 (IPA III).

Table 2³⁵. Age Structure and Condition of the Vehicle Fleet of the State Transport Inspectorate (as of March 1st, 2025)

Source: *Ministry of Transport, Analysis of Organizational and Personnel Structure, Condition of the Vehicle Fleet and Inspection Supervisions in the State Transport Inspectorate*, p.4.

Web link: <https://mtc.gov.mk/mk-MK/ministerstvo/drzaven-inspektorat-za-transport>. Accessed on 12 March 2025.

No.	Vehicle model and type	Year of manufacture	Vehicle type, engine power (kW) and engine displacement (cm ³)
1.	Ford Fiesta	2001	passenger / 44 kW / 1.299 cm ³
2.	Ford Fiesta	2001	passenger / 44 kW / 1.299 cm ³
3.	Skoda Fabia	2000	passenger / 74 kW / 1.390 cm ³
4.	Volkswagen Golf 3 Caravan	1997	passenger / 66 kW / 1.896 cm ³
5.	Peugeot 306 Caravan	2000	passenger / 66 kW / 1.997 cm ³
6.	Seat Ibiza	1995	passenger / 44 kW / 1.391 cm ³
7.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1995	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
8.	Opel Corsa	1998	passenger / 44 kW / 1.686 cm ³
9.	Opel Corsa	1998	passenger / 44 kW / 1.686 cm ³
10.	Seat Ibiza	1996	passenger / 44 kW / 1.398 cm ³
11.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1996	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
12.	Skoda Felicia	1995	passenger / 44 kW / 1.289 cm ³
13.	Skoda Felicia	1996	passenger / 44 kW / 1.289 cm ³
14.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1995	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
15.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1996	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
16.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1995	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
17.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1995	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
18.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1995	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
19.	Skoda Felicia	1996	passenger / 44 kW / 1.289 cm ³
20.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1996	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
21.	Volkswagen Polo Fox	1996	passenger / 33 kW / 1.043 cm ³
22.	Opel Astra	2001	passenger / 55 kW / 1.199 cm ³
23.	Volkswagen Caddy	2007	passenger / 51 kW / 1.997 cm ³
24.	Audi A3	1998	passenger / 66 kW / 1.896 cm ³

³⁵ The registration plates of the passenger motor vehicles are not shown in the table.

From the data presented in Table 2, it can be concluded that, of the total number of passenger motor vehicles available to the Inspectorate, the oldest date back to 1995. Specifically, seven (7) passenger motor vehicles were manufactured in 1995; seven (7) in 1996; one (1) in 1997; three (3) in 1998; two (2) in 2000; three (3) in 2001; and one (1) in 2007. In summary, out of a total of twenty-four (24) passenger motor vehicles, the average age of the Inspectorate's vehicle fleet, based on an analysis conducted as of 1 March 2025, is 27.6 years.

In addition to the shortcomings of the vehicle fleet, which negatively affect the mobility of inspectors in the field, it is important to emphasize the persistent risk to inspectors' personal safety when conducting inspections of supervised entities. These risks may take various forms, including verbal threats, endangerment of personal security, violations of physical and/or psychological integrity, and the forcible seizure and/or destruction of official and/or personal documents and objects.

4. CONCEPTUAL OUTLOOK TOWARD THE FUTURE AND THE ESTABLISHMENT OF A MODERN EUROPEAN INSPECTION SERVICE

The transport system is not a closed entity and transcends national borders, as it is mutually coherent and interconnected. Segments of the road network passing through the territory of the Republic of North Macedonia form part of the European transport corridors. Rapid technological development necessitates the advancement and implementation of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS), modeled on those in highly developed countries, which contribute to safer, more efficient, and more sustainable transport of passengers and goods. Such systems are essential for the development of a national transport network that meets European standards.

In this context, alongside investments in a modern and intelligent road network, efforts must also be directed toward transforming the State Transport Inspectorate into a modern inspection service capable of adopting and exchanging best practices and experiences with its European counterparts in order to keep pace with the digital era. To this end, the Inspectorate, in cooperation with the EU Delegation in Skopje, prepared a Twinning Project application aimed at strengthening its administrative and technical capacities. On 22 February 2024, an international public call was published for the selection of a Twinning Partner, with a submission deadline of 6 May 2024. The selection process concluded successfully with the appointment of a Polish–Croatian consortium composed of experts from the Chief Inspectorate of Road Transport of the Republic of Poland and the Ministry of the Sea, Transport, and Infrastructure of the Republic of Croatia.

The project officially commenced in Skopje in November 2024 and has a duration of 24 months, with the possibility of a three-month extension. A grant in the amount of EUR 1.3 million was approved for the project through the European Union's Instrument for Pre-Accession Assistance 2021–2027 (IPA III).

The general objective of the Twinning Project³⁶ is to enhance road transport safety in the Republic of North Macedonia and to achieve full alignment of national legislation with European Union standards in this area. The specific objectives focus on strengthening the operational capacities and administrative efficiency of the Inspectorate through the

³⁶ <https://javnaadministracija.mk/2025/01/29/mt-tvining-proekt-poddrshka-na-inspekciskite-sluzhbi-za-prevoz-na-patniczi-i-stoki/>. Accessed on 31 March 2025.

proper implementation of national and EU standards for inspection supervision of passenger and goods transport operators.

With regard to its contribution to the European integration process, the project aims to further harmonize national transport legislation with EU law and to strengthen the capacities of national authorities responsible for drafting and implementing transport legislation, including administrative, inspection, and other technical capacities.

A particularly significant aspect of the Twinning Project is the scope of cooperation, which includes approximately 50 expert missions involving 28 Polish and 14 Croatian experts. These missions represent a valuable opportunity for the exchange of know-how, capacity building, and the achievement of measurable results through the transfer of specialized technical knowledge and best practices.

5. CONCLUSION

The Ministry of Transport – State Transport Inspectorate represents one of the key pillars in the institutional framework for road traffic safety, and its functioning has a direct impact on the safety and security of passenger and goods transport. Through this professional paper, an effort has been made, within the limits of scientific observation, to present the role of the Inspectorate within the current institutional framework governing road traffic, emphasizing that this role must be complementary and coherent with that of other stakeholders in the sector.

Despite numerous objective and subjective challenges and risk factors affecting both the quality and quantity of its operational performance, the Inspectorate, although operating under significant strain, manages to fulfill its defined objectives using the available human and technical–technological resources. During the three-year period from 2022 to 2024, a total of 13,034 inspections were conducted. This corresponds to an average of 465.5 inspections per inspector over the three-year period, or an annual average of 155.16 inspections per inspector, which constitutes a respectable result under the given circumstances.

The Inspectorate largely succeeds in implementing planned regular inspections, achieving an implementation rate of 88.62% over the analyzed three-year period. Moreover, it exceeded the planned number of extraordinary inspections by 11.73%, while the overperformance rate for follow-up inspections reached 48.32%.

Additionally, during the same period, the number of detected irregularities exceeded projections by 71.47% (4,916 detected irregularities compared to 2,867 expected). The success rate in identifying specific and more complex irregularities will largely depend not only on the recruitment and continuous professional development of qualified staff but also on the modernization and technical upgrading of the Inspectorate through the introduction of advanced technological tools for timely detection. The subsequent processing of these irregularities, however, depends on the readiness and efficiency of judicial and misdemeanor bodies to ensure lawful, effective, and timely prosecution and sanctioning.

Finally, through the presentation of statistical and analytical indicators, this paper has reflected on the current state of road traffic while offering a theoretical conceptualization of the Inspectorate's role and future direction. With the implementation of ongoing projects in cooperation with the European Union, the State Transport Inspectorate is expected to strengthen its operational and technical capacities and to take a significant step toward becoming a modern inspection service aligned with contemporary demands and guided by the best practices of leading European inspection bodies in the transport sector.

REFERENCES:

1. Agreement on the International Carriage of Perishable Foodstuffs (ATP), 1970. UNECE, Geneva.
2. Annual Report on Inspection Supervision of the State Transport Inspectorate for 2024, Ref. No. 01-90, dated 30.01.2025.
3. Commission Staff Working Document. North Macedonia 2024 Report. Brussels, 30.10.2024. SWD(2024) 693 final. https://enlargement.ec.europa.eu/north-macedonia-report-2024_en. Accessed on 30 March 2025.
4. European Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road (ADR), 1957. UNECE, Geneva.
5. European Agreement concerning the Work of Crews of Vehicles Engaged in International Road Transport (AETR), 1970. UN, Geneva.
6. First Semiannual Report on Inspection Supervision of the State Transport Inspectorate for 2022, dated 19.07.2022.
7. First Semiannual Report on Inspection Supervision of the State Transport Inspectorate for 2023, Ref. No. 01-1006, dated 10.07.2023.
8. Law on Cable Cars and Ski Lifts (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia” No. 54/00, 103/08, 23/11, 53/11, 163/13 and 146/15 and “Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia” No. 285/20 and 224/24).
9. Law on Inspection Supervision (“Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia” No. 102/19, 272/24 and 22/25).
10. Law on Inspection Supervision (“Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia” No. 135/25).
11. Law on Misdemeanors (“Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia” No. 96/19 and 253/23).
12. Law on Public Roads (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia” No. 84/08, 52/09, 114/09, 124/10, 23/11, 53/11, 44/12, 168/12, 163/13, 187/13, 39/14, 42/14, 166/14, 44/15, 116/15, 150/15, 31/16, 71/16 and 163/16 and “Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia” No.174/21, 253/23 and 224/24).
13. Law on Road Transport (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia” No. 68/04, 127/06, 114/09, 83/10, 140/10, 17/11, 53/11, 6/12, 23/13, 120/13, 163/13, 187/13, 42/14, 112/14, 166/14, 44/15, 97/15, 124/15, 129/15, 193/15, 37/16, 71/16, 64/18, 140/18 and 163/18 and “Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia” No. 275/19, 67/22, 170/24, 3/25, 17/25 and 101/25).
14. Law on the Prohibition and Prevention of Performing Unregistered Activity (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia” No.199/14 and 147/15 and “Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia” No. 18/20 and 86/25).
15. Law on the Transport of Dangerous Goods in Road and Rail Traffic (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia” No. 92/07, 147/08, 161/09, 17/11, 54/11, 13/13, 163/13, 38/14, 166/14, 116/15, 193/15, 31/16 and 64/18 and “Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia” No. 288/21, 170/24 and 101/25).
16. Law on Working Time of Mobile Workers in Road Transport and Recording Devices (“Official Gazette of the Republic of Macedonia” No. 140/18 and “Official Gazette of the Republic of North Macedonia” No. 224/24, 101/25 and 192/25).
17. Ministry of Interior. Summary Analysis of Total Crime 2010–2023. <https://mvr.gov.mk/analiza/soobrakjaj/72>. Accessed on 3 January 2025.

18. Organizational Chart of the Ministry of Transport and its constituent bodies. <https://mtc.gov.mk/mk-MK/ministerstvo/drzaven-inspektorat-za-transport>. Accessed on 12 March 2025.
19. Practical Guide on Contract Procedures for EU External Actions (PRAG). <https://wikis.ec.europa.eu/display/ExactExternalWiki/ePRAG>. Accessed on 31 March 2025.
20. Second Semiannual Report on Inspection Supervision of the State Transport Inspectorate for 2022, Ref. No. 01-68, dated 13.01.2023.
21. Second Semiannual Report on Inspection Supervision of the State Transport Inspectorate for 2023, Ref. No. 01-51, dated 12.01.2024.
22. State Statistical Office. Passenger and Freight Transport for the Period 2010–2023. https://makstat.stat.gov.mk/PXWeb/pxweb/en/MakStat/MakStat__Transport__PatenTransport/560_Trans_MK_T39_ml.px/chart/chartViewLine/?rxid=46ee0f64-2992-4b45-a2d9-cb4e5f7ec5ef Accessed on 12 March 2025.
23. Twinning Project MK 22 IPA TR 01 24. Supporting the Inspection Services for Transportation of Passengers and Goods. <https://javnaadministracija.mk/2025/01/29/mt-tvining-proekt-poddrshka-na-inspekciskite-sluzhbi-za-prevoz-na-patniczi-i-stoki/>. Accessed on 31 March 2025.